

REVIEW

OPEN ACCESS

Innovations in Wastewater Treatment: A Nanotechnology Perspective

Nitish Dhingra^{1*}¹Electron Microscopy & Nanoscience Lab, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana – 141004, Punjab (India)²School of Organic Farming, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana – 141004, Punjab (India)

*Correspondence for materials should be addressed to ND (email: nitishdhingra@pau.edu)

Received:

2025/01/20

Accepted:

2025/02/12

Published:

2025/02/16

Abstract

The progressive industrialization and urbanization of the modern world have resulted in substantial amounts of wastewater, containing a plethora of toxic contaminants that pose serious threats to public health and the environment. As conventional treatment methods often fall short in terms of efficiency and efficacy, novel approaches like nanomaterial-based wastewater purification have received a lot of interest. Owing to their distinctive characteristics, nanomaterials have emerged as promising options for wastewater purification. This paper examines the recent developments in nanotechnology applied to wastewater treatment, highlighting the use of various novel nanomaterials such as metallic nanoparticles, graphene and its derivatives, carbon nanotubes, dendrimers, nanocomposites, nanofiltration membranes, clay nanomaterials, and polymeric nanomaterials, to achieve high adsorption capacities ranging from 80 % to 99.9 %. The mechanisms underlying the purification processes along with the targeted contaminants, removal efficiency and reusability of various nanomaterials are also outlined. Furthermore, the paper also discusses the challenges and future directions of nanomaterial-based wastewater treatment, considering its environmental and practical implications.

Keywords: Carbon nanotubes; Clay; Nanomaterials; Nanocomposites; Purification; Wastewater

Introduction

Water is a scarce commodity that is vital for human survival and economic development. However, the rapid population growth, industrialization, and urbanization have led to the contamination of freshwater sources. It is estimated that approximately 80% of the wastewater produced worldwide is released into the environment untreated, which has posed serious health and environmental challenges (United Nations, 2021). In order to safeguard public health and the environment, efficient treatment solutions are needed for pollutants such as heavy metals, organic compounds, and pathogens. The efficacy, affordability, and removal of complex contaminants by conventional wastewater treatment techniques such as filtration, coagulation, and biological processes are often limited in terms of their low removal efficiency, generation of secondary pollutants, and consumption of high energy (Saravanan et al., 2021). The increasing global need for water, combined with the growing shortage of clean water resources, has prompted researchers to seek more cost-effective and environmentally friendly solutions for wastewater treatment. In this context, nanomaterials have attracted a lot of interest because of their unique properties, which include high surface area, reactivity, mechanical strength and the capacity to undergo modifications to improve adsorption, catalysis, and photocatalysis (Khan et al., 2022; Yadav et al., 2024). Nanomaterials are the materials having at least one dimension in the range of 1-100 nm. These materials find applications in a variety of forms such as nanoparticles, nanofibers, nanotubes and nanomembranes. They can efficiently adsorb or catalytically treat a wide range of contaminants, including heavy metals, organic pollutants, and pathogens. Due to this ability, they serve as an effective solution to tackle current problem of water contamination, especially in areas where conventional wastewater treatment techniques are insufficient. Additionally, the application of nanomaterials has been found to enhance the effectiveness of the existing wastewater treatment technologies, including activated sludge and membrane filtration, by significantly improving their efficiency and capacity.

Nanomaterials are used in wastewater treatment through a variety of techniques, such as membrane filtration, adsorption, photocatalysis, and sophisticated oxidation processes. Each of these approaches makes use of the distinct properties of nanomaterials to get rid of contaminants such as pesticides, heavy metals, pharmaceuticals and pathogens. These techniques are especially appealing due to their high efficiency, affordability, and simplicity of usage. Furthermore, nanomaterials can be easily fabricated and tailored to target specific contaminants, which makes it possible to achieve better purification outcomes (Sadegh et al., 2017). Moreover, nanomaterials exhibit exceptional stability and endurance, rendering them exceedingly versatile and eco-friendly choices for the long-term wastewater treatment.

Although the use of nanomaterials in wastewater treatment has been widely explored, yet there is a significant knowledge gap in terms of understanding the robustness, scalability and potential toxicity associated with the use of nanomaterials in wastewater treatment. Some studies have revealed the environmental toxicity associated with the use of nanomaterials. Shivaji et al. (2023) carried out a study to explore the environmental toxicity caused by release of secondary pollutants in the form of ionic species by cadmium sulfide (CdS) quantum dots (QDs). CdS is an excellent semiconductor with suitable bandgap and band-edge positions that make it an attractive choice for applications in solar cells, photocatalysis, and bioimaging. However, the leaching of toxic cadmium (Cd^{2+}) metal ions due to the poor photocorrosion stability of CdS is a matter of grave concern. In order to prevent the leaching of toxic Cd^{2+} ions and hinder photocorrosion, the biofunctionalization of the active surface of CdS QDs was done by employing tea leaf extract. Another study by Lee et al. (2022) reported the effect of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) and zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnONPs) on zebrafish embryos in aquatic environment. The study revealed that introduction of these nanoparticles into natural water samples cause a significant acute toxicity to zebrafish embryos. Therefore, continued research is essential to ensure that these materials can be utilized effectively without endangering the environment further. This paper attempts to provide a comprehensive review of several novel nanomaterials based wastewater treatment strategies, evaluating their effectiveness along with challenges and future perspectives in this evolving field.

Types of Nanomaterials for Wastewater Purification

To implement nanomaterials for wastewater treatment, it is crucial to consider various parameters such as the extent to which contaminants are to be removed, efficiency of the nanomaterial, its recyclability, cost and environmental impact. Prior knowledge of the nanomaterial properties, characteristics and functions is required to decide on the type of contaminant to be removed from water. A diverse array of nanomaterials has been explored for wastewater treatment, including nanoparticles, carbon-based nanomaterials, dendrimers, nanocomposites, nanofiltration membranes, clay and polymeric nanostructures. Each category of nanomaterials offers different mechanisms for pollutant removal.

Nanoparticles

Metal and Metal Oxide nanoparticles

Metal nanoparticles, particularly those synthesized from titanium dioxide (TiO_2), silver (Ag), copper (Cu), and iron (Fe) have demonstrated significant capabilities in wastewater treatment. For example, TiO_2 nanoparticles (NPs) have been extensively studied for their photocatalytic properties, enabling the degradation of organic pollutants under UV light exposure. Their high surface area facilitates the adsorption of organic contaminants, while their photocatalytic activity further enhances the degradation process (Chen et al., 2020). Kholief et al. (2024) reported photocatalytic degradation of organic contaminants using TiO_2 NPs synthesized from ilmenite following different leaching methods and by using different acids such as HCl, HNO_3 and Aqua Regia. The effect of different parameters such as addition rate, reaction time, ilmenite grain size, reaction temperature and acid-ilmenite ratio was also studied. The efficacy of TiO_2 NPs for photocatalytic degradation was observed to be dependent on several parameters, including dose, agitation forces, light intensity, starting concentration, pH, time, and temperature. The reaction conditions of 600 mg/l dose, 200 rpm agitation force for 60 minutes of spinning, 800 lx light intensity, 10 mg/l starting concentration, pH 7.5, time of 90 minutes, and 298 (K) temperature were found to be the most favorable for TiO_2 NPs/UV photocatalytic degradation. The removal percentages of total nitrogen (TN), chemical oxygen demand (COD), biological oxygen demand (BOD), and total suspended solids (TSS) were also investigated. The maximum removal percentage of TN, BOD, and COD after secondary treatment were conducted using mixture of TiO_2 NPs, ferric chloride, and chitosan, which reached 94.9, 99.7 and 99.6%, respectively. Overall, the findings of the study revealed that TiO_2 NPs hold promising photodegradation potential for removal of organic

contaminants from sewage water. Mehta and Bhushan, 2024 reported a study on green and cost-effective method for the synthesis of TiO₂ NPs using leaf and stem extracts of *Carissa opaca*. The synthesized TiO₂ NPs were characterized using various analytical techniques and they were observed to have spherical/hexagonal crystalline structure with the average particle size ranging from 72.8 to 84.11 nm. The biosynthesized TiO₂ NPs showed outstanding photocatalytic activity against methylene blue (MB), with decolorizing efficiencies of 87.8% and 91.95%, respectively. In contrast, decolorizing efficiencies of 82.1% and 71.9% was observed against methyl violet (MV).

Silver is used for disinfecting drinking water alone or in conjunction with agents such as hydrogen peroxide. At certain doses, they are only marginally poisonous to animal cells, but they are highly toxic to bacteria like *E. Coli*. Silver Nanoparticles (AgNPs), known for their antimicrobial properties, disrupt microbial cell walls and biochemical pathways, thus effectively eliminating pathogens in wastewater (Palani et al., 2023). AgNPs can be synthesized by inert gas condensation (IGC), co-condensation, microemulsion, chemical reduction, UV photoreduction, and microwave assisted synthesis. Over 700 bacteria present in waste water treatment plants have been shown to be effectively eliminated by AgNPs. The microorganisms are targeted by AgNPs through more than three different mechanisms. This suggests a reduced likelihood of mutation for developing resistance. AgNPs are efficacious even at extremely low concentrations. The DNA of microorganisms is bound by the silver ions, which inhibits them from absorbing phosphorous and salt, which are essential for their transport processes. Additionally, this stops the respiratory processes that are essential for the survival of the cell. The antimicrobial properties of AgNPs are correlated with their size. Smaller the size of AgNPs, better is their antimicrobial strength. This is because the smaller size NPs can easily penetrate through the cytoplasm, resulting in enhanced interaction between NPs and the microbial cells and its organelles. The possible mechanism of AgNPs interaction with the microbial cells is depicted in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. The possible mechanism of AgNPs interaction with the microbial cells

AgNPs are also used for UF processes as antifouling membranes. The enhanced surface area resulting from size reduction helps in the effective adsorption of organic matter present in water samples. Another significant development in this direction is the hybrid use of AgNPs in combination with other polymers, which has been observed to be an efficient technique for removing heavy metals from wastewater (Ganguly et al., 2021). For example, AgNPs complexed with the Schiff base N-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-biphenyl-4-amine is found to be effective for the elimination of Cu²⁺ ions (Bhargava and Uma, 2019). Ali et al. (2018) studied the removal of heavy metal ions from aqueous solutions by impregnating cotton cellulose with AgNPs using co-precipitation method. The batch experiments conducted to study the adsorption of metal ions revealed that adsorption takes place very fast and equilibrium is attained within 30 mins. The metal-ions affinity of cotton-AgNPs composite was found to be in the order Hg²⁺ > Ni²⁺ > Cr³⁺ > Co²⁺ > Pb²⁺. Moreover, filtration of cotton-AgNPs composite is quite convenient.

Copper oxide nanoparticles (CuO NPs) are also frequently employed in wastewater treatment due to their small size, natural abundance of precursors, large surface area, non-toxic nature and low-production cost. The most common approaches for the synthesis of CuO NPs are precipitation and microwave heating. The highest reported adsorption capacity of CuO NPs for fluoride removal from the aqueous phase is 3152 mg/g (Ighalo et al., 2021). For the adsorption of dyes and heavy metals from water using CuO NPs, the best-fit kinetics and isotherm models is the pseudo-second order model (R² > 0.99) and Langmuir model (R² > 0.99), respectively. The thermodynamic analysis

revealed that the adsorption by CuO NPs was primarily spontaneous and endothermic. Moreover, in most cases, CuO NPs can be recycled up to five times with a recovery rate of more than 80% for contaminants.

Nanoscale zero-valent iron (nZVI) is a core-shell composite consisting Fe⁰ core coated with ferric oxide layer. Due to their relatively low-cost, excellent adsorption capacity and high reactivity, ZVI NPs are also utilized for the reduction of heavy metals, such as chromium (Cr), arsenic (As), mercury (Hg), and cadmium (Cd) through chemical reactions that convert them into less harmful forms (Tarekegn et al., 2021; Phenrat et al., 2019). The different types of interactions between nZVI and metal/metalloid ions are summarized in Table 1. In many circumstances, a combination of these interaction types happens, depending on the system's redox potential (oxidized/reduced form of the metal or metalloid) and the nZVI's capping layer. The systems with significantly higher positive potential than Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺/Fe are often reduced, and the reduced form can precipitate on or near the nZVI surface (common examples include Cr, Hg, Ag, As, Cu, U, and Se ions). Metal ions in systems with a little higher positive redox potential than Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺/Fe can be reduced as well as adsorbed. Metal ions from systems with similar or higher negative redox potential than that of Fe²⁺/Fe³⁺/Fe are largely adsorbed on the oxide/hydroxide or capping layer of nZVI without reduction (examples include Zn and Cd ions).

Table 1. Types of interaction between nZVI and metal/metalloid ions.

Interaction type	Examples	References
Adsorption	As, Cr, Pb, Ni, Zn, Se, Co, Cd, Ba ions	Filip et al. (2019); Garg et al. (2024)
Co-precipitation	As, Cr, Ni, and Se ions	Filip et al. (2019); Garg et al. (2024)
Oxidation/Reoxidation	As, U, Se, and Pb ions	Filip et al. (2019); Garg et al. (2024)
Precipitation	Co, Cd, Cu, Pb, and Zn ions	Filip et al. (2019); Garg et al. (2024)
Reduction	As, Cr, Cu, U, Pb, Ni, Se, Co, Pd, Pt, Hg, Ag ions	Filip et al. (2019); Garg et al. (2024)

Yang et al. (2020) used biochar-supported nanoscale zero-valent iron (nZVI-BC) to adsorb As(III) and Cd(II) from aqueous solution at pH ranges of 5-8 and 3-5, with absorption capacities of 158.5 and 179.9 mg/g, respectively. The nZVI is also capable of removing organic chemicals such as dyes from the wastewater. Khashij et al. (2020) reported the removal of RB5 (reactive black 5) dye using nZVI synthesized via green route using *Thymus vulgaris* leaf extract. At pH 4, RB5 dye was removed from water with 99% efficiency.

Magnetic nanoparticles

Magnetic nanoparticles (MNPs), such as iron oxide nanoparticles, offer the advantage of easy separation from wastewater using an external magnetic field post-treatment or by centrifugation and filtration. MNPs have been employed for the removal of heavy metals such as lead (Pb), mercury (Hg), and cadmium (Cd) due to their high surface reactivity and adsorption capacity. Studies have shown that MNPs can adsorb heavy metals effectively, thus highlighting their utility in contaminated water treatment processes (Akchiche et al., 2021; Farahbakhsh et al., 2021). However, the bare MNPs get oxidized rapidly and undergo aggregation, therefore, surface modification of these MNP is desired. Furthermore, ferrite NPs have low stability which demands for functionalized magnetic nanocomposites to employ in wastewater purification. As a result, magnetite silica nanocomposites (Kokate et al., 2013), magnetite-graphene nanocomposites (Abu-Nada et al., 2020), chitosan-magnetite nanocomposites (Cheraghpour and Pakshir, 2020), magnetite nanoparticle coated sand (Sorwat et al., 2021), and other materials are being investigated for water purification with improved performance and cost effectiveness.

Carbon-Based Nanomaterials

Activated Carbon Nanomaterials

Activated carbon derived from various biomass sources has been modified at the nanoscale to improve its adsorption capabilities. Nanoscale activated carbon exhibits a larger surface area and porous structure, which are essential for efficient adsorption of various contaminants, including dyes and pharmaceuticals (Sophia and Lima, 2018). et al. explored the use of activated carbon to remove heavy metal ions from water and observed high adsorption capacities of 95% and 86% for Pb²⁺ and Cd²⁺ ions, respectively (Dong et al., 2018). In a study by Bali et al. (2019), commercial activated carbon was used to remove heavy metal ions. The adsorption equilibrium for Cd²⁺ took 15

minutes, while Pb^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Cu^{2+} required 45 minutes. The percentage removal was 64% for all ions, with Cd^{2+} having the highest removal rate. The various type of carbon based nanomaterials are summarized in Figure 2.

Graphene and its Derivatives

Graphene is a two-dimensional material composed of carbon atoms arranged in a hexagonal lattice structure. The high surface area (~2630 m²/g) and excellent mechanical and chemical properties make it highly effective for wastewater treatment, especially in adsorbing heavy metals, organic pollutants, and pathogens. Its two-dimensional structure allows for rapid adsorption and removal of various contaminants. Studies have shown that graphene can be functionalized with oxygen or nitrogen-containing groups to enhance its adsorption capacity and selectivity for heavy metal ions. For example, oxygen-functionalized graphene has demonstrated superior adsorption of lead (Pb^{2+}), cadmium (Cd^{2+}), and arsenic (As^{3+}) from wastewater, significantly outperforming conventional adsorbents such as activated carbon (Jayakaran et al., 2019).

On the other hand, graphene oxide (GO) is a derivative of graphene that contains oxygen functional groups, such as hydroxyl, carboxyl, and epoxy groups. These functional groups provide GO with a higher reactivity and dispersibility in water, making it more suitable for wastewater treatment applications. Graphene and GO have received attention due to their exceptional mechanical, electrical, and thermal properties. Their high surface area allows for effective adsorption and removal of organic and inorganic pollutants. Moreover, GO can be functionalized to enhance its affinity for specific contaminants, leading to increased treatment efficiency (Mohammed et al., 2024). GO interacts with heavy metal ions primarily through electrostatic attraction and complexation. The negatively charged oxygen functional groups on GO can attract positively charged metal cations, such as lead (Pb^{2+}), cadmium (Cd^{2+}), mercury (Hg^{2+}), and chromium (Cr^{6+}), forming stable metal-oxygen bonds. This allows GO to efficiently remove these toxic metals from wastewater. GO can remove both organic pollutants and heavy metals through electrostatic interactions and chemical bonding (Liu et al., 2019).

Because of its remarkable features, graphene and its derivatives have a promising future in high-frequency devices (Colmiais et al., 2022; Routray et al., 2020), electronics (Arshad et al., 2022), biochemical and medical sensors, photodetectors (Benjamin et al., 2022; Yusof et al., 2022), and energy storage devices (Wang et al., 2022; Kumar et al., 2022). Furthermore, they are known to extend the life of batteries. They also have the potential for usage in solar cells, supercapacitors, and wastewater treatment (Table 2).

Table 2. Applications of graphene-based nanocomposites.

Composite	Application	Ref.
Au-GO and Au-rGO	Surface enhanced Raman Scattering and Catalysis	Yu et al. (2018)
Ag-GO and Ag-rGO	Catalysis, Biosensing	Qian et al. (2020)
TiO ₂ -GO	Photocatalysis	Wang et al. (2019)
ZnO-rGO	Photovoltaics	Sha et al. (2021)
Graphene-Cu/Ni	Transistor	Jr. et al. (2020)
MnO ₂ -GO	Supercapacitor	Kumar et al. (2022)

Carbon Nanotubes

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are cylindrical nanostructures made of carbon atoms arranged in hexagonal lattice in the tube partitions that are capped at the ends with half of a fullerene-like structure. CNTs are known for their unique properties such as high mechanical strength, conductivity, chemical stability and large surface area. CNTs effectively adsorb organic pollutants like dyes, pesticides, pharmaceuticals, and personal care products due to their high surface area and porous structure (Aslam et al., 2021). The surface functional groups on CNTs can bind to heavy metal ions such as lead, mercury, arsenic, and chromium, effectively removing them from wastewater. The hybridization of carbon atom differentiates between two types of CNTs, namely, single-walled (SWCNT) and multi-walled (MWCNT). The diameter of SWCNTs is generally close to 1 nm with several thousand times longer in length. On the other hand, MWCNTs can be seen as a series of compressed SWCNTs having different diameters. As a result, the MWCNTs can have diameters up to 100 nm. Functionalized MWCNTs have been found to significantly enhance the adsorption capacities for these metals compared to traditional adsorbents. Compared to MWCNTs, SWCNTs have a greater adsorption capacity (Gupta et al., 2013). Various studies have highlighted their effectiveness in adsorbing heavy metals, organic pollutants, and even microorganisms through a combination of van der Waals forces and electrostatic interactions.

The CNTs have been shown to effectively adsorb heavy metals, organic pollutants, and dyes through π - π interactions and surface modifications (Kurwadkar et al., 2019)). These have been integrated into filtration membranes to enhance the quality of treated water by preventing the passage of undesirable substances (Arora and Attri, 2020). The CNTs are superior to activated carbon; but, due to their high manufacturing costs, their large-scale applications for efficient wastewater treatment are limited. Additionally, because of their hydrophobic surface, CNTs should be retained in aqueous solutions employing surfactants to prevent aggregation, which could reduce their active surface area.

Fig. 2. Structure of graphene, carbon nanotube, graphene oxide and Fullerene

Barrejon et al. (2019) synthesized cross-linked CNT adsorbents for water treatment. The researchers used bisdiazonium compounds consisting of benzidine derivatives for cross-linking SWCNTs. It was observed that the resulting product had an excellent adsorption capacity and good recyclability to remove the organic contaminants and oils from the water. Moreover, by controlling the degree of cross-linking, it was possible to tune the specific area, porosity and the adsorption capacity of the resulting adsorbent. Bakar et al. (2021) produced CNTs with encapsulated iron NPs by making use of waste cooking palm oil and tested their potential for the removal of heavy metals ions from the wastewater. Optimizations, including varying adsorbent dose, initial pH solution, and heavy metal ions, were examined. The observed optimal adsorbent dosage was 1.8 g/L in a 100 mg/L Cu (II) solution at neutral pH (pH 7). Its application in a highly acidic solution (pH 2) resulted in Cu (II) ions removal rate of around 80%. Further, the synthesized CNTs effectively removal heavy metal ions in the order: Fe(II) > Zn(II) \approx Cu(II) with removal rates ranging from 99.2% to 99.9%.

Dendrimers

Dendrimers are artificially created, highly branched polymers and nanohybrid materials that integrate both organic and inorganic elements (Figure 3). Dendrimers exhibit a wide range of properties such as multivalency, chemical stability, self-assembly, low cytotoxicity and solubility. Such properties make them useful in wastewater treatment applications. Dendrimers possess the ability to enclose organic pollutants and can release them when subjected to certain stimuli, enabling focused removal. Additionally, polymer-based nanospheres can trap chemicals that break down pollutants, releasing active substances when encountering target contaminants. Studies have been performed to combine dendrimers with magnetic NPs to boost the rate of dye removal from wastewater and to eliminate the subsequent steps such as filtration and centrifugation. The reduction in processing steps and energy consumption enhances the likelihood of dendrimers adoption in wastewater treatment.

Galangash et al. (2018) observed the removal of Acid Red 114 (AR114) and Black 5 (RB5) dyes from the aqueous solution using magnetic polyhydroxyl modified Fe₃O₄@SiO₂-TRIS NPs. In another study conducted by Duan et al. (2019), a porous polyamidoamine (PAMAM) dendrimer gel adsorbent was synthesized which was had the ability to purify contaminated water by filtration of methyl orange (MO) and tartrazine (TTZ) dyes. Dendrimers are also employed in the removal of heavy metals from water. Using a divergent method, Gajjar et al. (2014) synthesized hydroxyl-terminated triazine-based dendrimers corresponding to different generations (G₁(OH)₈,

$G_2(OH)_3$, and $G_3(OH)_{12}$). Their potential as adsorbents was assessed for the removal of Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Ni^{2+} ions from water. The study revealed that $G_3(OH)_{12}$ exhibited the highest removal ability which increased with the pH. The properties that make dendrimers suitable for wastewater treatment are the large surface area, highly branched and variable structure with accessible internal cavities and functionalized surface.

Fig. 3. Structure of a dendrimer

Nanocomposites

Nanocomposites combine two or more different materials, at least one of which must be on the nanoscale. The nanomembrane consisting of organic and inorganic NPs, is an example of a nanocomposite material. Such materials can enhance the water treatment efficiency substantially. For instance, the integration of carbon-based nanomaterials such as graphene oxide with metal nanoparticles has shown remarkable efficacy in treating complex wastewater streams. Nanocomposites with CNTs, graphene and a semiconducting metal oxide such as TiO_2 or ZnO , not only enhances the removal efficiency of pollutants but also promotes electron transfer processes during photocatalytic treatment (Memisoglu et al., 2023). Nanocomposites involving combination of conductive polymers and metal NPs can be used for the removal of pollutants through simultaneous adsorption and photocatalytic degradation (Rhazi et al., 2018). Biopolymer-nanomaterial composites can be utilized to enhance bioremediation processes by improving microbial attachment and metabolic activity. The common contaminant, *E. Coli*, present in wastewater, can be easily treated using Ag nanocomposite. Thus, Ag nanocomposite serves as an effective antibacterial agent (Bruna et al., 2021).

Nanofiltration Membranes

Nanofiltration membranes are emerging technology for wastewater treatment. It is a type of membrane filtration that employs a semi-permeable membrane with less than 10 nm pore sizes. Nanomembranes lie between ultrafiltration (UF) and reverse osmosis (RO) membranes and are capable of removing divalent ions such as Mg^{2+} , Ca^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Pb^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} (Peydayesh et al., 2020). Nanomembranes have pore sizes smaller than heavy metal ions, therefore, application of pressure allows water molecules to pass through the membranes while blocking heavy metal ions and other contaminants (Mahmoud et al., 2021). Nanocomposite membranes synthesized by combining nanofillers with polymeric membrane matrices can significantly enhance the heavy ions filtration efficiency of nanofiltration membranes. The incorporation of nanoparticles can lead to enhanced permeability, selectivity and antibacterial properties of nanofiltration membranes toward specific contaminants (Esfahani et al., 2019). Graphene membranes, utilized for their exceptional filtration properties, can filter out salts and organic pollutants with high efficiency. Similarly, Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) can be engineered for specific molecular sieving, allowing them to target and remove particular contaminants from wastewater streams.

Clay Nanomaterials

Clay minerals, such as montmorillonite (MMT), kaolinite, and bentonite, have been extensively studied for their potential in wastewater treatment applications due to their natural abundance, low cost, and high adsorption capacity (Wang and Wang, 2019). Clay nanomaterials, when modified or combined with functional groups, can enhance pollutant removal efficiencies in wastewater. Several methods have been explored to enhance the properties of clay nanomaterials, including modification with organic compounds, metal ions, or even incorporation into nanocomposites.

Clay-based nanomaterials can effectively adsorb heavy metals such as lead, cadmium, and mercury from contaminated water. Xie et al. (2024) reported that MMT has promising capability for removing heavy metals due to its high cation exchange capacity and surface area. The adsorption efficiency can be further enhanced by surface modifications using functional groups that provide active sites for the adsorption of metal ions.

In addition to heavy metals, clay nanomaterials have been explored for the removal of organic pollutants, including dyes and pharmaceuticals. Studies show that modified clay minerals can adsorb large quantities of organic dyes from wastewater, thus serving as effective adsorbents (Gamoudi and Srasra, 2019). The synergistic effect of clay minerals combined with activated carbon has proven to further enhance the removal efficiency of organic contaminants in wastewater. The clay-based nanomaterials also depict potential for catalytic applications in the degradation of organic pollutants. Fatimah et al. (2022) reported that clay-supported catalysts have ability to facilitate chemical oxidation reactions, which can break down complex organic molecules. The use of light-activated clay nanomaterials for photocatalytic degradation of contaminants is also being actively researched.

Polymer Nanomaterials

Polymer nanomaterials have emerged as promising solutions for wastewater purification due to their unique properties, such as high surface area, tunable chemistry, and improved stability. These nanomaterials can be designed to selectively remove contaminants from wastewater, making them an attractive alternative to traditional treatment methods. One of the most widely used polymer nanomaterials for wastewater purification is polymeric nanoparticles. These nanoparticles can be synthesized using various techniques, such as emulsion polymerization or sol-gel methods. By controlling the size, shape, and surface chemistry of the nanoparticles, their adsorption capacity and selectivity towards specific contaminants can be tailored. For example, polymeric nanoparticles modified with chelating agents have been shown to effectively remove heavy metal ions from wastewater (Ayalew et al., 2022). The high surface area and small size of the nanoparticles enable them to interact with contaminants more efficiently, leading to enhanced removal efficiencies.

Another class of polymer nanomaterials that has gained significant attention for wastewater purification is polymer nanofibers. These nanofibers can be produced using electrospinning, a technique that involves the application of an electric field to a polymer solution, resulting in the formation of fibres with diameters in the nanoscale range. High surface area and porosity of the nanofibers make them ideal for adsorption and filtration applications. Functionalization of the nanofibers with specific groups can further enhance their selectivity towards certain contaminants. Polymeric nanofibers modified with carboxyl or amino groups have been used for the removal of heavy metal ions and organic pollutants from wastewater (Tian et al., 2011).

Polymer nanomaterials can also be used as membranes for wastewater purification. These membranes can be prepared using various techniques, such as phase inversion or layer-by-layer deposition. By controlling the porosity and surface chemistry of the membranes, they can be designed to selectively allow the passage of water while rejecting contaminants. Polymeric membranes modified with hydrophilic groups have been used for the removal of organic pollutants from wastewater (Aravind et al., 2021). The high water permeability and mechanical stability of these membranes make them suitable for large-scale applications.

In addition to their use in adsorption and filtration, polymer nanomaterials can also be used as catalysts for the degradation of contaminants in wastewater. Polymeric nanoparticles modified with metal oxides have been used for the photocatalytic degradation of organic pollutants (Tripathy et al., 2024). The high surface area and tunable surface chemistry of the nanoparticles enable them to interact with contaminants more efficiently, leading to enhanced degradation rates.

Table 3 presents a comparative analysis of various nanomaterials being explored for wastewater treatment. Many of the nanomaterials can be highly efficient (removal efficiency > 95%) for wastewater treatment, however their reusability and economic cost have to be also taken into account.

Mechanisms of Nanomaterial-Based Wastewater Purification

The unique properties of nanomaterials such as small size, high surface area, and tunable surface chemistry enable various mechanisms for removing pollutants from the wastewater. The key mechanisms (Figure 4) involved in this process are described in the following subsections.

Adsorption

Adsorption is the most common mechanism employed by nanomaterials for the removal of various pollutants. It involves the adhesion of pollutants (adsorbates) onto the surface of the nanomaterial (adsorbent) due to physical or chemical interactions. The effectiveness of adsorption depends on factors like the nanomaterial's surface area, pore size distribution, surface chemistry, and the nature of the pollutant. Activated carbon, CNTs and Metal-Organic Frameworks (MOFs) are examples of nanomaterials which follow adsorption for the pollutant removal.

Catalytic Degradation

Some nanomaterials act as catalysts or catalyst supports, accelerating the degradation of pollutants into less harmful substances. The catalytic degradation can be photocatalysis or electrocatalysis. Photocatalysis utilizes semiconductor nanomaterials like titanium dioxide that generate electron-hole pairs upon light irradiation, leading to the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) which degrade pollutants. On the other hand, electrocatalysis employs nanomaterials as electrodes or electrocatalysts to drive redox reactions that degrade pollutants. Metallic nanoparticles such as silver or palladium can catalyze the degradation of organic pollutants through electrocatalysis.

Membrane Filtration

Nanomaterials can be incorporated into membranes to enhance their performance in wastewater treatment by reducing pore size and improving selectivity for specific pollutants. These nano-enhanced membranes offer improved permeability, selectivity, and antifouling properties. This involves nanofiltration and reverse osmosis. Nanofiltration employs membranes with pore sizes in the nanometer range, effectively removing dissolved organic matter, multivalent ions, and some viruses. Reverse osmosis utilizes membranes with even smaller pores, capable of removing almost all dissolved salts and organic molecules. Examples of such nanomaterials include CNT and GO membranes. The GO membranes exhibit excellent separation properties for water purification due to their unique two-dimensional structure.

Bioremediation

Certain nanomaterials possess antimicrobial properties, effectively inactivating or removing pathogens from wastewater. Nanomaterials like silver nanoparticles release ions that disrupt bacterial cell membranes and inhibit their growth. In addition, similar to photocatalytic degradation, reactive oxygen species (ROS) generated by photocatalytic nanomaterials can also inactivate microorganisms. Examples include silver NPs, widely known for their antimicrobial properties, used in various applications, including water disinfection. Zinc Oxide NPs also exhibit photocatalytic activity that can inactivate bacteria and viruses. Keskin et al. (2018) used the electrospun cyclodextrin ultrathin fibers (CD-F) to encapsulate the bacteria and studied the capability of resulting CD-F/bacteria biocomposite to remove heavy metal ions such as Ni(II) and Cr(VI) and textile dye RB5 from wastewater. The removal efficiency of Ni(II), Cr(VI), and RB5 by the CD-F/bacteria biocomposite was found to be $70 \pm 0.2\%$, $58 \pm 1.4\%$, and 82 ± 0.8 , respectively. The study revealed that improved performance of CD-F/bacteria biocomposite can be attributed to the fact that the bacteria may use CD as an additional carbon source to speed up their growth.

In addition, electrocoagulation, which works by generating coagulants in situ through electrochemical reactions that can effectively destabilize and aggregate contaminants, can be also useful for wastewater treatment. This process can be synergistic with nanomaterial adsorption or catalytic degradation, as it enhances the removal efficiency of suspended solids, heavy metals, and organic contaminants. Examples include kinetic modelling of peat water treatment with continuous electrocoagulation using aluminium electrodes, treatment of tropical peat water in Sarawak peatlands nature reserve by utilizing a batch electrocoagulation system, treatment of Borneo midstream river water affected by palm oil plantation run-off with sustainable batch electrocoagulation system and application of batch electrocoagulation treatment system with aluminium electrodes for simultaneous removal of organic and heavy metal contaminants from Borneo urban rivers.

Advantages of Nanomaterial-Based Wastewater Purification

Nanomaterial-based wastewater treatment offers several advantages over conventional methods that make it an increasingly important technology in water treatment. These include high surface area and reactivity, selective contaminant removal, energy efficiency, improved filtration performance, the ability to target emerging contaminants, cost-effectiveness, scalability, and

environmental sustainability (Kusworo et al., 2021). Due to these benefits nanomaterial-based purification is envisaged as a promising solution to the growing global challenges of water contamination and scarcity.

Fig. 4. Pictorial representation of nanomaterials wastewater purification mechanisms.

High surface area and enhanced adsorption capacity

Nanomaterials possess an exceptionally high surface area to volume ratio, providing abundant active sites for adsorption, catalysis, and other treatment processes. This characteristic significantly enhances their efficiency in removing a wide range of pollutants compared to bulk materials.

Tunability and selectivity

The properties of nanomaterials, such as size, shape, surface chemistry, and composition, can be precisely tailored during synthesis. This tunability allows for the development of highly selective and efficient nanomaterials for targeting specific pollutants from complex wastewater matrices (Shanaah et al., 2023).

Table 3. A comparative analysis of various nanomaterials used for wastewater treatment.

Nanomaterial	Target contaminant	Removal Efficiency (%)	Reusability	Reference
TiO ₂ nanoparticles	Methylene Blue Dye, Heavy Metals	80-90%	Moderate	Aravind et al. (2021); Tripathy et al. (2024)
Iron oxide nanoparticles	Heavy metals, Dyes	85-95	High; magnetic separation aids reuse	Aragaw et al. (2021)
Graphene and its derivatives	Organic pollutants, pathogens	90-99	High; depends on chemical modification	Anegbe et al. (2024)
Carbon nanotubes	Dyes, heavy metals	90-95	Moderate; functionalization improves	Arora and Attri (2020)
Dendrimers	Dyes, heavy metals	> 90	Moderate; improves with functionalization	Wazir et al. (2020)
Nanocomposites	Heavy metals, oil residues	> 90	Moderate	Hazmi et al. (2024)
Nanofiltration membranes	Salts, heavy metals	95-99	High	Maroufi and Hajilary (2023)
Clay nanomaterials	Organic contaminants	85-95	Moderate	Chuaicham et al. (2023)
Polymer nanomaterials	Oil, microplastics	~85%	Moderate, limited by polymer degradation	Tripathy et al. (2024); Muhamad et al. (2021)

Efficient catalytic ability

Numerous nanomaterials, such as titanium dioxide (TiO₂) and zinc oxide (ZnO), act as photocatalysts. Such materials generate ROS when exposed to UV or visible light, which can degrade a wide range of organic pollutants, including pesticides, pharmaceuticals, and dyes.

Cost effectiveness and reusability

While initial investment in nanomaterial synthesis can be high, the long-term operational costs might be lower due to high efficiency and reusability of nanomaterials in water purification processes. Nanomaterials such as magnetic NPs allow efficient separation of contaminants from water by applying external magnetic field and can be regenerated for multiple uses (Zahmatkesh et al., 2023).

Low energy requirement

Nanomaterial-based treatment processes often operate at lower temperatures and pressures compared to conventional methods, reducing energy consumption. Moreover, certain nanomaterial-based processes, like photocatalysis, can be driven by sunlight, thus minimizing energy requirements.

Challenges and Future Prospects

Despite the promising potential, several challenges hinder the widespread adoption of nanomaterials based wastewater treatment. Firstly, the synthesis and production of some nanomaterials can be expensive which can limit their large-scale application. Their small size enables them to penetrate biological membranes, possibly leading to adverse effects. The potential toxicity of nanomaterials and their release into the environment require careful assessment and mitigation strategies. Developing scalable and cost-effective methods for manufacturing and deploying nanomaterials while ensuring their long-term performance and stability is crucial.

The future research in this field should focus on the creation of multifunctional nanomaterials that can simultaneously perform adsorption, catalysis, and antimicrobial activity. These materials can provide comprehensive treatment solutions, addressing multiple contaminants in a single process. Hybrid nanomaterials combining graphene, metal oxides, and functionalized surfaces could target a broader range of pollutants, including organic, inorganic, and microbial contaminants. Efforts must be put towards developing environmentally friendly nanomaterials that are biodegradable, non-toxic, and derived from sustainable sources.

These materials would address concerns regarding the ecological impact and long-term fate of nanoparticles in the environment. Integration of nanomaterials with supportive matrices, such as membranes or larger particulate carriers, can help in easier recovery and reuse, mitigating environmental risks. Biodegradable polymer-based nanomaterials and bio-inspired nanomaterials derived from natural substances like chitosan, cellulose, and lignin could provide greener alternatives to traditional nanomaterials. Fouling is a major issue in membrane-based filtration technologies. Therefore, research must be carried out on the nanomaterials with self-cleaning and anti-fouling properties that can prolong the lifespan of filtration systems and reduce maintenance costs. Nanocomposite membranes embedded with anti-fouling agents like silver nanoparticles or graphene oxide can resist biofilm formation, preventing clogging and performance degradation.

Conclusion

Nanomaterial-based wastewater treatment systems present a promising avenue for confronting the global water crisis and ameliorating environmental contamination. The unique properties of nanomaterials offer a superior alternative to traditional methods, enabling enhanced efficiency, reduced energy consumption, and improved water quality. Nonetheless, the successful integration and sustainable application of these technologies hinge upon the resolution of several critical challenges, including the potential ecotoxicological implications, economic feasibility, material stability under operational conditions, and scalability for widespread adoption. Addressing these intricacies is paramount to the realization of their full potential and the attainment of universal access to clean, potable water. Key solutions include developing functionalized and composite nanomaterials to enhance performance and recovery, promoting green synthesis to reduce toxicity and costs, and establishing regulatory frameworks to ensure safe deployment. While challenges abound, continued research and development in this field will be crucial in achieving clean, safe, and accessible water for all.

References

- Abu-Nada A, McKay G, Abdala A (2020) Recent advances in applications of hybrid graphene materials for metals removal from wastewater. *Nanomaterials* 10(3):595. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano10030595>.
- Akchiche Z, Abba AB, Saggai S (2021) Magnetic nanoparticles for the Removal of Heavy Metals from industrial wastewater: Review. *Algerian Journal of Chemical Engineering* 1(1):8-15. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4458444>.
- Ali A, Mannan A, Hussain I, et al. (2018) Effective removal of metal ions from aqueous solution by silver and zinc nanoparticles functionalized cellulose: Isotherm, kinetics and statistical supposition of process. *Environmental Nanotechnology Monitoring and Management* 9:1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enmm.2017.11.003>.
- Anegbe BA, Ifijen IH, Maliki M, et al. (2024) Graphene oxide synthesis and applications in emerging contaminant removal: a comprehensive review. *Environmental Sciences Europe* 36:15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12302-023-00814-4>.
- Aragaw TA, Bogale FM, Aragaw BA (2021) Iron-based nanoparticles in wastewater treatment: A review on synthesis methods, applications, removal mechanisms. *Journal of Saudi Chemical Society* 25:101280. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jscs.2021.101280>.
- Aravind M, Amalanathan M, Mary MSM (2021) Synthesis of TiO₂ nanoparticles by chemical and green synthesis methods and their multifaceted properties. *SN Applied Sciences* 3:409. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-021-04281-5>.
- Arora B, Attri P (2020) Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs): A Potential Nanomaterial for Water Purification. *Journal of Composites Science* 4(3):135. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcs4030135>.
- Arora B, Attri P (2020) Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs): A Potential Nanomaterial for Water Purification. *Journal of Composites Science* 4(3):135. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jcs4030135>.
- Arshad MU, Dutta D, Sin YY, et al. (2022) Multi-functionalized fluorinated graphene composite coating for achieving durable electronics: Ultralow corrosion rate and high electrical insulating passivation. *Carbon* 195:141–153. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2022.04.004>.
- Aslam MMA, Kuo HW, Den W, et al. (2021) Functionalized Carbon Nanotubes (CNTs) for Water and Wastewater Treatment: Preparation to Application. *Sustainability* 13(10):5717. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13105717>.
- Ayalew ZM, Guo X, Zhang X (2022) Synthesis and application of polyethyleneimine (PEI)-based composite/nanocomposite material for heavy metals removal from wastewater: A critical review. *Journal of Hazardous Materials Advances* 8:100158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hazadv.2022.100158>.
- Bakar SA, Jusoh N, Mohamed A, et al. (2021) Carbon nanotubes from waste cooking palm oil as adsorbent materials for the adsorption of heavy metal ions. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 28:65171-65187. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-14918-y>.
- Bali M, Tlili H (2019) Removal of heavy metals from wastewater using infiltration-percolation process and adsorption on activated carbon. *International Journal of Environmental Science and Technology* 16:249-258. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13762-018-1663-5>.
- Barrejon M, Syrgiannis Z, Burian M, et al. (2019) Cross-linked carbon nanotube adsorbents for water treatment: Tuning the sorption capacity through chemical functionalization. *ACS Applied Materials and Interfaces* 11(13):12920-12930. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.8b20557>.
- Benjamin SR, Junior EJMR (2022) Graphene-Based electrochemical sensors for detection of environmental pollutants. *Current Opinion in Environmental Science and Health* 29:100381. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coesh.2022.100381>.
- Bhargava S, Uma V (2019) Rapid extraction of Cu (II) heavy metal from industrial waste water by using silver nanoparticles anchored with novel Schiff base. *Separation Science and Technology* 54:1182–1193. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01496395.2018.1527853>.
- Bruna T, Maldonado-Bravo F, Jara P, et al. (2021) Silver nanoparticles and their antibacterial applications. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences* 22(13):7202. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms22137202>.

- Chen D, Cheng Y, Zhou N., et al. (2020) Photocatalytic degradation of organic pollutants using TiO₂-based photocatalysts: A review. *Journal of Cleaner Production* 268:121725. DOI: 10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121725.
- Cheraghipour E, Pakshir M (2020) Process optimization and modeling of Pb(II) ions adsorption on chitosan-conjugated magnetite nano-biocomposite using response surface methodology. *Chemosphere* 260:127560.
- Chuaicham C, Trakulmututa J, Shu K, et al. (2023) Recent Clay-Based Photocatalysts for Wastewater Treatment. *Separations* 10(2):77. <https://doi.org/10.3390/separations10020077>.
- Colmiaes I, Silva V, Borme J, et al. (2022) Towards RF graphene devices: A review. *FlatChem* 35:100409. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.flatc.2022.100409>.
- Dong L, Hou L, Wang Z, et al. (2018) A new function of spent activated carbon in BAC process: removing heavy metals by ion exchange mechanism. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 359:76–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2018.07.030>.
- Duan Y, Song Y, Zhou L (2019) Facile synthesis of polyamidoamine dendrimer gel with multiple amine groups as super adsorbent for highly efficient and selective removal of anionic dyes. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science* 546:351-360. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcis.2019.03.073>.
- Esfahani MR, Aktij SA, Dabaghian Z, et al. (2019) Nanocomposite membranes for water separation and purification: Fabrication, modification, and applications. *Separation and Purification Technology* 213:465-499. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2018.12.050>.
- Farahbakhsh J, Vatanpour V, Ganjali MR, Saeb MR (2021) Magnetic nanoparticles in wastewater treatment. *Woodhead Publishing Series in Electronic and Optical Materials: Sawston, United Kingdom*, pp 547-589. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-823688-8.00036-3>.
- Fatimah L, Fadillah G, Yanti L, Doong R (2022) Clay-Supported Metal Oxide Nanoparticles in Catalytic Advanced Oxidation Processes: A Review. *Nanomaterials* 12(5):825. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano12050825>.
- Filip J, Kolařík J, Petala E, et al. (2019) Nanoscale Zerovalent iron particles for treatment of metalloids. *Springer International Publishing AG: Cham, Switzerland*, pp 157-199. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-95340-3_4.
- Gajjar D, Patel R, Patel H, et al. (2014) Removal of heavy metal ions from water by hydroxyl terminated triazine-based dendrimer. *Desalination and Water Treatment* 55(5):1209-1219. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19443994.2014.922446>.
- Galangash MM, Ghavidast A, Bozorgpanah Z (2018) Adsorption of acid red 114 and reactive black 5 in aqueous solutions on dendrimer-conjugated magnetic nanoparticles. *Journal of Chinese Chemical Society* 66(1):62-74. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jccs.201800177>.
- Gamoudi S, Srasra E (2019) Adsorption of organic dyes by HDPy⁺-modified clay: Effect of molecular structure on the adsorption. *Journal of Molecular Structure* 1193:522-531. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2019.05.055>.
- Ganguly K, Dutta SD, Patel DK, Lim KT (2021) Silver nanoparticles for wastewater treatment. *Elsevier: Amsterdam, The Netherlands*, pp 385–401. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-821141-0.00016-1>.
- Garg R, Mittal M, Tripathi S, et al. (2024) Core to concept: synthesis, structure, and reactivity of nanoscale zero-valent iron (NZVI) for wastewater remediation. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 31:67496-67520. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-024-33197-x>.
- Gupta VK, Kumar R, Nayak A, et al. (2013) Adsorptive removal of dyes from aqueous solution onto carbon nanotubes: a review. *Advances in Colloid and Interface Science* 193–194:24-34. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cis.2013.03.003>.
- Hazmi HEA, Luczak J, Habibzadeh S, et al. (2024) Polysaccharide nanocomposites in wastewater treatment: A review. *Chemosphere* 347:140578. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chemosphere.2023.140578>.
- Ighalo JO, Sagboye PA, Umenweke G, et al. (2021) CuO nanoparticles (CuO NPs) for water treatment: A review of recent advances. *Environmental Nanotechnology Monitoring and Management* 15:100443. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enmm.2021.100443>.

Jayakaran P, Nirmala GS, Govindarajan L (2019) Qualitative and quantitative analysis of graphene-based adsorbents in wastewater treatment. *International Journal of Chemical Engineering* 2019:9872502. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2019/9872502>.

Jr GM, Cerqueira MF, Borme J, et al. (2020) Field-effect transistors made of graphene grown on recycled copper foils. *Materials Chemistry and Physics* 256:123665. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matchemphys.2020.123665>.

Keskin NOS, Celebioglu A, Sarioglu OF, et al. (2018) Encapsulation of living bacteria in electrospun cyclodextrin ultrathin fibers for bioremediation of heavy metals and reactive dye from wastewater. *Colloids and Surfaces B: Biointerfaces* 161:169-176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfb.2017.10.047>.

Khan Y, Sadia H, Shah SZA, et al. (2022) Classification, Synthetic, and Characterization Approaches to Nanoparticles, and Their Applications in Various Fields of Nanotechnology: A Review. *Catalysts* 12(11):1386. DOI: 10.3390/catal12111386.

Khashij M, Dalvand A, Mehralian M, et al. (2020) Removal of reactive black 5 dye using zero valent iron nanoparticles produced by a novel green synthesis method. *Pigment and Resin Technology* 49(3):215-221. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PRT-10-2019-0092>.

Kholief MG, Hesham AEL, Hashem FS, et al. (2024) Synthesis and utilization of titanium dioxide nano particle (TiO₂ NPs) for photocatalytic degradation of organics. *Scientific Reports* 14:11327. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-53617-9>.

Kokate M, Garadkar K, Gole A (2013) One pot synthesis of magnetite-silica nanocomposites: applications as tags, entrapment matrix and in water purification. *Journal of Materials Chemistry A* 1(6):2022-2029.

Kumar R, Samykano M, Ngui WK, et al. (2022) Investigation of thermal performance and chemical stability of graphene enhanced phase change material for thermal energy Storage. *Physics and Chemistry of the Earth, Parts A/B/C*. 128:103250. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pce.2022.103250>.

Kumar RR, Thanigaivel S, Priya AK, et al. (2022) Fabrication of MnO₂ nanocomposite on GO functionalized with advanced electrode material for supercapacitors. *Journal of Nanomaterials* 2022:7929270. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/7929270>.

Kurwadkar S, Hoang TV, Malwade K (2019) Application of carbon nanotubes for removal of emerging contaminants of concern in engineered water and wastewater treatment systems. *Nanotechnology for Environmental Engineering* 4:12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41204-019-0059-1>.

Kusworo TD, Kumoro AC, Aryanti N, et al. (2021) Removal of organic pollutants from rubber wastewater using hydrophilic nanocomposite rGO-ZnO/PES hybrid membranes. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering* 9(6):106421. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2021.106421>.

Lee YL, Shih YS, Chen ZY, et al. (2022) Toxic Effects and Mechanisms of Silver and Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles on Zebrafish Embryos in Aquatic Ecosystems. *Nanomaterials* 12:717. DOI: 10.3390/nano12040717.

Liu X, Ma R, Wang X, et al. (2019) Graphene oxide-based materials for efficient removal of heavy metal ions from aqueous solution: A review. *Environmental Pollution* 252:62-73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2019.05.050>.

Mahmoud AED, Fawzy M, Abdel-Fatah MMA (2021) Technical aspects of nanofiltration for dyes wastewater treatment. Springer: Berlin/Heidelberg, Germany, pp 23-35. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-4823-6_2.

Maroufi N, Hajilary N (2023) Nanofiltration membranes types and application in water treatment: a review. *Sustainable Water Resources Management* 9:142. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40899-023-00899-y>.

Mehta M, Bhushan I (2024) Potential of biosynthesized titanium dioxide nanoparticles towards wastewater treatment and antimicrobial activity. *3 Biotech* 14:66. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13205-024-03915-w>.

Memisoglu G, Murugesan RC, Zubia J, et al. (2023) Graphene nanocomposite membranes: fabrication and water treatment applications. *Membranes* 13(2):145. <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes13020145>.

Mohammed MN, Aljibori HSSS, Jweeg MJ, et al. (2024) A comprehensive review on graphene oxide based nanocomposites for wastewater treatment. *Polish Journal of Chemical Technology* 26(1):64-79. <https://doi.org/10.2478/pjct-2024-0007>.

Muhamad Ng SN, Idrus S, Ahsan A, et al. (2021) Treatment of wastewater from a food and beverage industry using conventional wastewater treatment integrated with membrane bioreactor system: A pilot-scale case study. *Membranes* 11(6):456. <https://doi.org/10.3390/membranes11060456>.

Palani G, Trilaksana H, Sujatha RM et al. (2023) Silver Nanoparticles for Waste Water Management. *Molecules* 28(8):3520. <https://doi.org/10.3390/molecules28083520>.

Peydayesh M, Mohammadi T, Nikouzad SK (2020) A positively charged composite loose nanofiltration membrane for water purification from heavy metals. *Journal of Membrane Science* 611:118205. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.memsci.2020.118205>.

Phenrat T, Lowry GV, Babakhani P (2019) Nanoscale Zerovalent iron (NZVI) for environmental decontamination: A brief history of 20 years of research and field-scale application. Springer International Publishing AG: Cham, Switzerland, pp 1-43. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-95340-3_1.

Qian Y, Zhou C, Zhou J, et al. (2020) Synthesis of silver-nanoparticles composite with highly catalytic activity supported on the reduced graphene oxide. *Applied Surface Science* 525:146597. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsusc.2020.146597>.

Rhazi ME, Majid S, Elbasri M, et al. (2018) Recent progress in nanocomposites based on conducting polymer: application as electrochemical sensors. *International Nano Letters* 8:79-99. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40089-018-0238-2>.

Routray KL, Saha S, Behera D (2020) Nanosized CoFe₂O₄-graphene nanoplatelets with massive dielectric enhancement for high frequency device application. *Materials Science and Engineering: B* 257:114548. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mseb.2020.114548>.

Sadegh H, Ali GAM, Gupta VK, et al. (2017) The role of nanomaterials as effective adsorbents and their applications in wastewater treatment. *Journal of Nanostructure in Chemistry* 7:1-14. DOI: 10.1007/s40097-017-0219-4.

Saravanan A, Kumar PS, Jeevanantham S, et al. (2021) Effective water/wastewater treatment methodologies for toxic pollutants removal: Processes and applications towards sustainable development. *Chemosphere* 280:130595. DOI: 10.1016/j.chemosphere.2021.130595.

Sha S, Lu H, Yang S, et al. (2021) One-step electrodeposition of ZnO/graphene composite film as photoanode for dye-sensitized solar cells. *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects* 63:127491. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfa.2021.127491>.

Shanaah HH, Alzaimoor EFH, Rashdan S, et al. (2023) Photocatalytic degradation and adsorptive removal of emerging organic pesticides using metal oxide and their composites: Recent trends and future perspectives. *Sustainability* 15(9):7336. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15097336>.

Shivaji K, Sridharan K, Kirubakaran D, et al. (2023) Biofunctionalized CdS Quantum Dots: A Case Study on Nanomaterial Toxicity in the Photocatalytic Wastewater Treatment Process. *ACS Omega* 8:19413-19424. DOI: 10.1021/acsomega.3c00496.

Sophia C, Lima EC (2018) Removal of emerging contaminants from the environment by adsorption. *Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety* 150:1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoenv.2017.12.026>.

Sorwat J, Mellage A, Maisch M, et al. (2021) Chromium (VI) removal kinetics by magnetite-coated sand: small-scale flow-through column experiments. *Journal of Hazardous Materials* 415:125648. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2021.125648>.

Tarekegn MM, Hiruy AM, Dekebo AH (2021) Nano zero valent iron (nZVI) particles for the removal of heavy metals (Cd²⁺, Cu²⁺ and Pb²⁺) from aqueous solutions. *RSC Advances* 11:18539. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d1ra01427g>.

The United Nations world water development report 2021: valuing water (2021) The state of water resources. Available at: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000375724> (accessed 23 September 2024).

Tian Y, Wu M, Liu RG, et al. (2011) Electrospun membrane of cellulose acetate for heavy metal ion adsorption in water treatment. *Carbohydrate Polymers*. 83(2):743–748. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbpol.2010.08.054>.

Tripathy J, Mishra A, Pandey M, et al. (2024) Advances in Nanoparticles and Nanocomposites for Water and Wastewater Treatment: A Review. *Water* 16:1481. <https://doi.org/10.3390/w16111481>.

Wang R, Shi K, Huang D, et al. (2019) Synthesis and degradation kinetics of TiO₂/GO composites with highly efficient activity for adsorption and photocatalytic degradation of MB. *Scientific Reports* 9:18744. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-019-54320-w>.

Wang W, Wang A (2019) *Nanoscale Clay Minerals for Functional Ecomaterials: Fabrication, Applications, and Future Trends*. Springer, Cham, pp 2409–2490. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-68255-6_125.

Wang Y, Chen J, Qin H, et al. (2022) Stress-assisted design of stiffened graphene electrode structure toward compact energy storage. *Journal of Energy Chemistry* 71:478–487. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jechem.2022.04.028>.

Wazir MB, Daud M, Ali F, et al. (2020) Dendrimer assisted dye-removal: A critical review of adsorption and catalytic degradation for wastewater treatment. *Journal of Molecular Liquids* 315:113775. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2020.113775>.

Xie S, Huang L, Su C, et al. (2024) Application of clay minerals as adsorbents for removing heavy metals from the environment. *Green and Smart Mining Engineering* 1:249–261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gsme.2024.07.002>.

Yadav KK, Cabral-Pinto MMS, Gacem A, et al. (2024) Recent advances in the application of nanoparticle-based strategies for water remediation as a novel clean technology—A comprehensive review. *Materials Today Chemistry* 40:102226. DOI: 10.1016/j.mtchem.2024.102226.

Yang D, Wang L, Li Z, et al. (2020) Simultaneous adsorption of Cd(II) and As(III) by a novel biochar-supported nanoscale zero-valent iron in aqueous systems. *Science of The Total Environment* 708:134823. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.134823>.

Yu J, Ma Y, Yang C, et al. (2018) SERS-active composite based on rGO and Au/Ag core-shell nanorods for analytical applications. *Sensors and Actuators B: Chemical*. 254:182–188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.snb.2017.07.034>.

Yusof NM, Ibrahim S, Rozali S (2022) Synthesis of Graphene Oxide-Cobalt Oxide Hybrid Materials for Gas Sensors Application. *Materials Today Proceedings* 66:2680–2684. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matpr.2022.06.494>.

Zahmatkesh S, Keshteli MH, Bokhari A, et al. (2023) Wastewater treatment with nanomaterials for the future: A state-of-the-art review. *Environmental Research* 216(3):114652. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2022.114652>.

Author Contributions

ND conceived the concept and prepared the manuscript. ND and NR reviewed and approved the manuscript.

Acknowledgements

The authors express their sincere thanks to the Director of Research and EMN laboratory, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana for the support to carry out research.

Funding

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

Not applicable.

Competing interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

Open Access *This article is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License, which permits use, sharing, adaptation, distribution, and reproduction in any medium or format, as long as you give appropriate credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if changes were made. The images or other third-party material in this article are included in the article's Creative Commons license unless indicated otherwise in a credit line to the material. If material is not included in the article's Creative Commons license and your intended use is not permitted by statutory regulation or exceeds the permitted use, you will need to obtain permission directly from the copyright holder. Visit for more details <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>.*

Citation: Dhingra N and Rani N (2025) Innovations in Wastewater Treatment: A Nanotechnology Perspective. *Environmental Science Archives* 4(1): 122-138.